

Degradation of Mesoporous Silica Materials in Biological Milieu: The Gateway for Therapeutic Applications

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Since early developments in the field of mesoporous materials, mesoporous silica has attracted large interest in drug delivery, as they display an ordered array of pores with diameters ranging from 2 to 50 nm, which can be loaded with drugs. Mesoporous silica dissolves at physiological pH, triggering the release of loaded drugs. Several studies have focused on determining the key factors that determine the biodistribution, biocompatibility, and toxicity both in vitro or in vivo. However, in vivo studies focused on the degradation of mesoporous silica materials are very scarce, despite its relevance for drug release. In this perspective, recent works addressing mesoporous materials degradation in the context of drug delivery are discussed, first from a physicochemical point of view, and secondly in in vivo settings, in animal models that are the closest conditions to the encountered when the mesoporous materials are administered to humans. Finally, further discussion about the future directions in the design of mesoporous nanomaterials for therapy and for the study of their biological fate are presented.

(in general in the nano-micro range) and shapes, but also as films with thicknesses around 100 nm. In all cases, MNs characteristically have a large and accessible specific surface, resulting from the porous structure of the material. The organized arrangement of spherical or channel-like pores defines the material properties. For more than 20 years, research on MNs has focused on optimizing the porous structure and functionality aiming to design materials with highly controllable properties and characteristics for applications in sensing, catalysis, adsorption of contaminants, filtration, as molecular sieves, as nanoreactors and in the biomedical field.^[4–23]

Since their discovery, people realized the potential of mesoporous nanoparticles (MNPs) as drug-delivery systems as it is a logical conclusion that pores can be

used to load drugs and utilized as drug containers for their delivery.^[9,21,22,24,25]

Both the external and inner surface, i.e., pores, of MNPs are usually easy to functionalize either during or after their synthesis.^[13,26] Functionalization with organic molecules or polymers allows tuning pore hydrophilicity/hydrophobicity, as well as to bring specific chemical functions to the pore walls. Pore chemistry defines the affinity of the pore wall for other molecules, and this tuneable affinity has been used as the principle for the loading of therapeutics. A wide variety of molecules of therapeutic relevance have been loaded in the pores of MNPs and films, aiming at a variety of biomedical applications: i.e., for cancer treatment, nosocomial diseases, etc.^[14,24,25,27] From a material science perspective, most works involving MNs for drug delivery address the optimization of the pore characteristics for drug loading. Extensive work has been performed controlling pore size and chemistry to achieve optimal drug loading, as well as on the engineering nanoparticle surface for ensuring circulation, targeting, and biocompatibility.^[9,27] However, one fundamental aspect that has been almost neglected in most of the works on mesoporous materials for drug delivery: porous materials must not only be designed for the loading of drugs but also for their release. Release can occur by differences of drug concentration inside and outside the pores. It can also be triggered by the degradation of the mesoporous materials in biological fluids. In an optimal situation, framework degradation and drug release must both occur at a desired pace and in specific organs or tissues after administration to the patient. MNs for drug delivery are usually based on silica (SiO₂).^[9] Together with aluminosilicates,

1. Mesoporous Oxides and Degradation Processes

Mesoporous oxide-based nanomaterials (MNPs) are defined as those presenting an ordered array of pores, with precisely controlled sizes in the 2–50 nm range. The oxide material is formed thanks to sol–gel reactions, while the pores are produced taking advantage of amphiphilic molecules that self-assemble in supramolecular structures that act as templates.^[1–3] MNPs can be produced as particles, with different shapes and sizes

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mesoporous SiO₂ were the first and subsequently most studied ordered mesoporous materials^[1,2,7,28] Silica hydrolyses in aqueous media lose of the pore organization. Degradation is understood as the process of erosion of the mesoporous material by dissolution of the silica in the media.

Several works dealt with the degradation of mesoporous materials in biological fluids *in vitro*, including some excellent reviews.^[9,29–31] On the contrary, in the literature about MNs degradation *in vivo* is scarce, to a large extent because of the difficulties in tracing the products of degradation *in vivo*.^[32–34] *In vitro* conditions are not necessarily transferable to *in vivo* situations and there is a significant gap in the knowledge of the behaviour of degradable MNs in the last condition.

In this perspective we will discuss recent works addressing silica-based MNs degradation in the context of drug delivery, first from a physicochemical point of view, and secondly through *in vivo* settings using animal models. Finally, we will further discuss future directions in the design of mesoporous nanomaterials for *in vivo* therapy and the study of their biological fate.

2. Physical Chemistry of the Degradation of Silica-Based MNs

In recent years, degradation mechanisms of silica prepared by sol-gel-based strategies have been clearly established in aqueous

media under physiological conditions. The degradation process, schematized in **Figure 1a**, can be divided into three steps: 1) the hydration of the silica surface; 2) the hydrolysis of siloxane bonds, giving rise to silanol (Si-OH) groups; and 3) ion-exchange processes, consisting of nucleophilic attacks of hydroxyl groups (OH⁻) that result in the leaching of silicic acid.^[29,30] These processes will occur on amorphous silica, regardless of thin films, nanoparticles or micrometric powders, but the kinetics of the process will depend on the material's characteristics.

For instance, the degradation of mesoporous silica thin films was assessed by ellipsometry, allowing easy monitoring of thickness and porosity of the films as a function of immersion time.^[35–40] Such analysis can be done under liquid flow, an experiment harder to perform when particles are involved. In a pioneer work, Bass et al.^[35–40] demonstrated that the dynamic behavior of mesoporous silica films exposed to aqueous solutions under biologically relevant conditions (PBS buffer, pH = 7.4) is shown to be highly dependent on composition, porosity, and calcination temperature. In addition, experiments performed using protein-containing media, with concentration comparable to the one present in the blood, showed that degradation occurs at a slower rate in the presence of proteins. This observation was attributed to a barrier effect to diffusion, caused by protein adsorption onto the porous film surface.^[38] Moreover, experiments performed in a variety of aqueous solutions demonstrated the silica framework increase its hydrolytic stability.^[35,36,39,40]

Figure 1. a) Representation of the intact structure of silica MNPs, its mechanism of degradation and factors that regulate the particles degradation. Reproduced with permission.^[30] Copyright 2017, Wiley. b–c) Transmission Electron Microscopy micrographs of silica MNPs before and (c) after suspension in SBF for 10 days. Adapted with permission.^[60] Copyright 2011 American Chemical Society.

On the contrary, in vitro degradation of silica MNPs has been carefully studied by several groups using particles with different characteristics under a wide variety experimental conditions.^[9,30,31,41] Though some experiments were performed under non-relevant biological conditions, most took into account the particularities of biological media, since their focus was to study the nanoparticles fate and toxicity. In fact, in several examples, simulated body fluids (SBF) were used to test the stability of MNPs. SBF solutions have the ionic composition of plasma but lack proteins and other biological molecules. Those studies helped to understand that several aspects determine the kinetic of the silica MNPs degradation, including: nanoparticle morphology, size and concentration, pore size, surface area, silica condensation degree, inorganic doping, surface functionalization, and the particular physiological medium used (see Figure 1a).^[9,29,30,41] Dissolution kinetics depends on the surface functionalization of the oxide. Izquierdo-Barba et al. described how organic functionalization in mesoporous silica can decrease the degradation rate of the mesostructures, in different cell culture conditions.^[42]

It is interesting to discuss in detail some of these works performed in vitro using MNPs, to gain insight into techniques that can be used to understand silica dissolution in biological media. Silica dissolution can be traced by measuring degradation products in contact with the MNPs as a function of contact time, as shown by Bein and coworkers.^[43] These authors demonstrated that the experimental conditions in which the silica particles are prepared influence their degradation rate under hydrolytic conditions. Degradation times between hours and weeks were found, when varying from pure silica materials prepared at acidic conditions to organically functionalized silica prepared in basic medium. They attributed the observed differences to changes in the network connectivity, measured by solid state magic angle spinning nuclear magnetic resonance, concluding that the lower the connectivity, the higher the hydrolytic degradability.

Understanding changes in size and morphology of mesoporous nanoparticles after exposure to biological media can be achieved with electron microscopy. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) provides a clear visual information about the changes in the morphology of the mesoporous particles, i.e., dissolution and reprecipitation of degradation products. As stated before, in biological fluids the nature of the coating of the mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN) and their concentration play a fundamental role in the speed and extend of mesoporous degradation. Silica has a solubility of 0.14 mg mL^{-1} in aqueous media at physiological pH, 7.4. If the total amount of silica present in the nanoparticles is lower than this concentration, MNPs will dissolve completely. However, silica can also reprecipitate with other ions present in the media and the products of precipitation may not be any longer soluble. The presence of proteins capable of entering the pores usually prevents the dissolution by adsorbing and thus coating the whole MNPs surface, forming a barrier for the hydrolysis of the pore wall and the release of ions. The process of degradation and re-precipitation usually results in aggregation and a clear loss of the spherical shape of nanoparticles. Such deformities and the related changes in porosity can be observed by TEM, monitoring samples at different time points during the degradation process, as shown in Figure 1b,c and 2a. The coating of the nanoparticles with

polyethylene glycol (PEG) has a clear impact on degradation. PEGylation acts as a barrier for re-precipitation preventing, to a certain extent, that re-precipitated silica attaches to the surface of the mesoporous nanoparticles. It does not avoid silica dissolution, but it seems to slow it down, as shown in the TEM images in Figure 2a, where samples with and without PEG coating subjected to dissolution are compared. PEGylation prevents proteins from blocking the pores, increasing the rate of dissolution compared with mesoporous nanoparticles without surface modifications, which block the pores with proteins and then dissolve slower. However, from TEM images it is difficult to assess how the pore arrangement is affected by the dissolution of silica. To address this issue we have recently used small angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) to study the organization of the pore array in MSN.^[44]

Before exposition to biofluids, MNPs presented a SAXS pattern characteristic of organized mesoporous silica with well-defined diffraction peaks, which can be fitted as a cubic $1a3d$ phase with a unit cell size of $a = 8.7 \text{ nm}$. In addition, a surface area of $1058.8 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ and a monodisperse mesopore diameter of 2.7 nm were determined using N_2 sorption measurements. When the particles are PEGylated the SAXS peaks attributed to the mesopores ordering become less defined, probably as a consequence of the partial attachment of PEG chains inside the pores. SAXS measurements were conducted on mesoporous particles exposed to SBF solutions at pH = 5 and pH = 7.4 and at concentrations below silica solubility (0.01 mg mL^{-1}), at silica solubility (0.14 mg mL^{-1}) and over solubility (1 mg mL^{-1}). The choice of SBF without proteins aims to study how the dissolution process is affected by pH and ionic strength and composition present in biofluids without the influence of proteins. At the concentrations below solubility, naked silica and PEGylated silica very quickly lose the SAXS peaks, meaning that pore arrangement is lost as expected through the dissolution of the pore walls, which should be fast at a low concentration of silica as theoretically the solvent can hold all the dissolved silica. At the solubility concentration of silica, we observe the same situation for the naked silica; however, for the PEGylated samples at the same concentration, the scattering signal can be observed in the first time point of the measurements, meaning that PEGylation does slow down degradation. At the higher concentration of silica (1 mg mL^{-1}), we observed a well-defined diffraction peak characteristic of organized mesopores, which is detectable up to 24 h (see SAXS patterns as a function of time, in Figure 2b). Although the experimental noise does not allow a very reliable cell parameter to be calculated, the relationship between the distances of the more intense diffraction peaks located at approximately $Q = 1.88 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ and $Q = 2.16 \text{ nm}^{-1}$ can be attributable to peaks [211] and [220] of the cubic phase and permits the estimation of a cubic cell constant of $ca. a = 8.2 \text{ nm}$. This value is substantially smaller than the original cell parameter of 8.7 nm . A slight increase in cell parameter is observed during the first 6 h of measurements (see evolution of this parameter as a function of time in Figure 2c), indicating that first there is a collapse of the structure followed by some swelling of the “softer” already hydrolyzed silica and followed by reprecipitation at the surface, as observed in a previous work.^[45] Interestingly, within the same time frame, we observed changes in the size of the particles in the Guinier region (see the evolution of the radii of gyration in

Figure 2. a) Representative TEM micrographs of mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MSN, above) and MSN-PEG (below) exposed to SBF for three time periods for a total silica concentration of 0.14 mg mL^{-1} . b) SAXS patterns as a function of time of bare MSNs suspended in SBF at a concentration of 1 mg mL^{-1} . The time intervals of exposure are reported in the legend in unit of hours. The diffraction peak is still retained after 24 h of degradation in SBF. SAXS curves are scaled for clarity. c) Radii of gyration estimated from SAXS (red squares) and the position of the [211] X-ray diffraction peak of the cubic mesophase (empty circles) as a function of incubation time in SBF. Reproduced with permission.^[44] Copyright 2022, Elsevier.

Figure 2c). It can be concluded that pore structure changes while the particles decrease in size. The simultaneous stopping of the oxide dissolution and particle degradation hints at re-precipitation of silica species taking place in the pores, which reduces the area exposed to the media affecting degradation kinetics. For PEGylated mesoporous silica nanoparticles at 1 mg mL^{-1} concentration, no changes were observed in the SAXS peaks over the timeframe of the measurements, suggesting that the pore arrangement remains unaltered. However, TEM images indicate that there is aggregation of the nanoparticles as time passes and some changes in the particles shape, which hint on silica dissolution and re-precipitation.

It is clear that most of the characteristics determining the dissolution kinetics can be controlled by adequately choosing the synthetic conditions, the thermal treatment and the additional functionalization of the MNPs. However, the number of variables that should be taken into account make it hard to compare the data on silica dissolution kinetics obtained from the literature.^[30]

3. From In Vitro to In Vivo

As expected, the conditions tested in vitro, even in the case of experiments performed in biological fluids, are far from the conditions that MNPs face in vivo.

The first main difference is that MNPs will be in contact with a flowing media, circulating among different organs. Products of dissolutions will be continuously removed from the medium and this situation should reduce re-precipitation and aggregation, which also should facilitate degradation in the hour scale. Moreover, in vivo, following nanomaterial administration, the concentration of silica is far from saturation conditions at physiological pH (typically 0.02 mg mL^{-1}).^[33,38]

On the contrary, it is well known that when synthetic materials are put in contact with a real biological fluid, they are quickly covered by resident proteins forming a structure known as protein corona (PC). The assembly of this PC is the very first interaction between any nanoparticle and the biological milieu.

Interestingly, although the PC forms almost immediately onto the particles after exposure to biological fluids, its composition can vary over time.^[46] However, it is established that the composition of the PC depends on several factors, including: particle size, particle shape, material, and surface charge.^[46–48] In the particular case of mesoporous silica particles, it has been demonstrated that particle morphology,^[49,50] pore diameter,^[51] and particle size^[52] have clear influence over the characteristics of the PC. The assembly of these proteins confers to the particles with a “new identity” that will determine their colloidal stability, biodistribution, toxicity, and clearance.^[46]

The presence of the PC may slow down or even prevent the MNPs degradation.^[21,38,41] Thus, the chemistry of the mesoporous materials coating, which determines the PC characteristics, will play a fundamental role on the materials hydrolysis and following structural changes. Dense PEG or other polymer coatings decrease or suppress protein deposition on the particles. In these cases, pores remain free from proteins but exposed to the media and can degrade faster than unmodified silica, since proteins may block the pores acting as a barrier for dissolution.^[38] This thesis would be used to explain our *in vivo* degradation study. In absence of proteins, PEG coatings may act as protective barriers and slow down the degradation compared with the non-coated mesoporous materials, as we discussed earlier.

Finally, the biodistribution of the particles should be considered, since the accumulation in certain organs (that will depend on the MNPs characteristics, see below) may lead to preferential degradation.

4. In Vivo Degradation Studies

Tracing nanomaterials *in vivo* is per se a complex task. A major drawback for carrying out studies of the degradation of MNs *in vivo* stems from the difficulties in visualizing and tracing them and their degradation products *in vivo*. Visualization of nanomaterials requires their labelling by fluorescent dyes or radioisotopes to facilitate imaging techniques that detect the nanomaterials in the body following administration, like positron emission tomography (PET) and single photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) for radiolabelled nanomaterials.^[53] Mesoporous materials have enough contrast to be detected by TEM in excised organs. Ion coupled plasma mass spectroscopy (ICP-MS) has been used for quantification of mesoporous uptake also in excised organs, despite background silica present in the body difficult its applicability. But how can MNs and their products of degradation be differentiated? The limited knowledge on the *in vivo* degradation of mesoporous nanomaterials is clearly one of the factors that is a drawback for clinical translation of MNPs as it is unknown how and when the loaded drugs are released, which bring uncertainties on the capacity of these materials for providing a therapeutic dosage of loaded drugs.

Biodistribution of silica MNPs has been studied by several groups, with a focus on toxicity, biocompatibility and effectiveness of the drug delivery approach.^[9,30,54–57] These studies demonstrated that size, surface functionalization, surface charge, particle shape and administration route have a strong influence on MNPs biodistribution.^[9,31,55,58,59] In addition, they show that MNPs are distributed in body tissues and are excreted primarily

via renal clearance.^[9,54] Interestingly, in general, these studies highlight how biocompatible these MNPs are, but nearly none of them show their impact on long-term exposure.

As stated before, *in vivo* studies, focused on understanding the mechanism of silica MNPs degradation are very scarce. Tracing the fate of mesoporous silica nanoparticles *in vivo* has additional difficulties compared with other types of nanoparticles, which do not dissolve and are stable during circulation.

A first approach to study the effect of a living organism over mesoporous silica was performed by subcutaneous local injection of particles dispersed in PBS into mice.^[34] The MNPs induced a small nodule in the injection site, whose size decreased as a function of time until its disappearance in less than 28 days, pointing toward silica dissolution. In those cases in which the particles could be retrieved, TEM and SAXS experiments demonstrated that the pore characteristics degraded over time. However, despite its very interesting approach, this work did not take into account of the circulation of the particles in the body, a key point for targeted drug delivery purposes.

To take into account silica MNPs circulation, a label is needed. However, a major problem encountered with MNPs in *in vivo* studies is that the chosen marker (fluorescent dye or radiolabel), may detach during circulation or be altered by enzymatic and redox environments *in vivo* if attached to their surface.^[57] In some cases this can be avoided if the label is loaded in the core of the NPs or covalently attached to the matrix of the NPs, for example, during synthesis. As explained before, silica MNPs degrade via the hydrolysis of silica in blood stream and, if attached to the core, the label may be released from the particles as well. The major difficulty in fate studies with MNPs is, however, how to visualize the degradation products and differentiate them from the nanoparticles.

A seminal work on *in vivo* fate studies of mesoporous nanoparticles by Chen et al. compared the biodistribution of solid (non porous) silica and MSN both labeled with ⁸⁹Zr, a β emitter.^[32] Studies were conducted, using PET and nanoparticles following intravenous administration. The labeling was conducted by complexing the Zr to the silanols of the nanoparticle surface. In the case of the solid silica, the labeling is restricted to the surface of the NPs. In the mesoporous nanoparticles, ⁸⁹Zr attaches to the walls of the pores. PET images after intravenous administration of solid silica in the mouse models showed that the activity of ⁸⁹Zr accumulated in the femur, while for the mesoporous silica particles the accumulation occurred mainly in the liver. Solid silica NPs are unlikely to accumulate in femur and the authors interpret this result as a detachment of the Zr from the particles surface. Zr complexes strongly to phosphate groups present in the hydroxyapatite of the bones. In the case of the MNPs the Zr remains trapped in the mesoporous structure and the activity pattern reflects the fate of the NPs, which accumulate in the liver presumably because of their size and aggregation. In this work the MNPs were not coated with PEG or other molecules that may protect them before administration and it can be expected that in bloodstream the particles will be covered by proteins and biomolecules. We have followed the same procedure for ⁸⁹Zr labeling but with MSNs that were coated with PEG (molecular weights of 5 and 7k).^[33] The coating with PEG should decrease deposition of proteins on the MNPs and impact of proteins on blocking pores. With these nanoparticles

we observed both accumulation of activity in the liver and in the femur, i.e., patterns observed for the solid silica nanoparticles and for the mesoporous nanoparticles in the previous work. In our experiments, the silica is more prone to hydrolysis as the surface is protected from proteins but not from the medium. Products of the particles degradation, such as Si (IV) containing ions and clusters including Zr, can easily diffuse through the PEG shell. The mix pattern of distribution shows that the release is not complete with Zr remaining attached to the nanoparticles during the timeframe of the studies, and therefore we observed activity in the liver and spleen and to some extent in the lungs. In a way, results are counterintuitive, since they show that the MNPs that are coated and protected with PEG are dissolving more than those that are unmodified. Our interpretation of our results and the differences observed with Chen et al. and on in vitro studies is that the unmodified particles can be coated by proteins, as a consequence, their surface is covered, resulting in less silica dissolution. The surface of PEGylated mesoporous nanoparticles, in contrast, remains uncovered and accessible for media, being capable to release ions and other products of degradation.

The major difficulty on tracing the fate of mesoporous silica nanomaterials in vivo is to differentiate between nanoparticles and products of degradation. To tackle this issue, we decided to build a core-shell structure based on solid silica cores and mesoporous silica shells, coated with PEG.^[33] We placed ⁸⁹Zr

either on top of the solid silica before assembling the mesoporous shell or after the synthesis of the mesoporous shell before PEG coating, as schematically depicted in Figure 3a. The location of the ⁸⁹Zr in tiny amounts, does not alter the structure of the core shell nanoparticles, which are identical in size and shape (see TEM images in Figure 3b), only differing in the location of the ⁸⁹Zr in the structure. Identical nanoparticles should have the same fate but Zr can have a different fate depending on where it is located. Thus, ⁸⁹Zr was used to prove the biodistribution of the particles as a whole when it is placed between the core and the shell, and to trace the particles and products of shell degradation when was placed in the shell.

Indeed, PET scans after IV administration show two different biodistribution patterns for each Zr labeling strategies, with a clear accumulation of the Zr in the femur when this is placed in the shell (see PET/CT images of mice injected with MSNs obtained at different times in Figure 4a). When the activity per organ is compared for both systems, following organ harvesting and gamma counting, we observe that the activity distribution largely differs in blood and heart, being much larger in the first 2 h for the shell-labeled sample (see results presented in Figure 4b). Activity in blood and heart indicate that the product of degradation (free Zr, is circulating. In contrast, in the case of the core labeling, most of nanoparticles are to be found, since practically the first measurements, in liver and spleen, organs where macrophages are present. For samples with Zr in the

Figure 3. Synthesis and characterization of ⁸⁹Zr-labeled core-shell silica nanoparticles: a) scheme of the NPs synthesis, labeled in the core (L-CORE) and in the shell (L-SHELL). b) TEM images of the dense silica cores and the core-shell NPs. Reproduced with permission.^[33] Copyright 2021, Wiley.

Figure 4. a) PET/CT images of mice injected with L-SHELL particles and L-CORE particles after 10 min and 2 h from injection. For each time point and type of NP, whole body coronal PET maximum intensity projections have been co-registered with 3D rendered CT images. Representative axial slices, co-registered with the corresponding CT slices, are also shown. Color scale bars refer to coronal images. b) Percentage of injected dose per gram of organ. Results from ex vivo measurements by gamma counter. Values are represented in red for L-CORE NPs and in blue for L-SHELL NPs. Reproduced with permission.^[33] Copyright 2021, Wiley.

mesoporous shell, a peak of activity in blood within 2 h is observed. Such signal is not present for the NPs that have Zr at the core, indicating that within a few hours the mesoporous shell is being degraded to a large extent. Interestingly, the accumulation of activity in the femur increases with the time during the whole scan period, probably meaning a continuous degradation of the MNPs accumulated in other organs.

Labeling core and shell of the particles separately allowed us to differentiate between the nanoparticle and the degradation products. These experiments have also permitted us to estimate a degradation time for the shell, i.e., of the mesoporous oxide, which is a rather important information for the use of the nanoparticles as drug delivery systems. Degradation time is likely to change with nanoparticle size, i.e., with the thickness of the shell, the nature of the coating, the chemistry of pore walls and the pore size.^[30] Also, if the NPs are loaded with a cargo, the nature of the loaded drug (hydrophilicity, molecular weight, etc.) will also have an effect on the material degradation. There is large potential to advance the knowledge on the MNPs dissolution in vivo. Experiments prove nanoparticle degradation, which would indeed prevent accumulation of silica nanoparticles in the body. Nevertheless, it would be necessary to assess fate of the nanoparticles in the long term, and the effect of multiple doses being delivered. In principle, the concentration of silica in the body should be way below the saturation concentration in solution and, consequently, a complete dissolution of the NPs should be expected. But silica can re precipitate too with other ions present in the blood hampering further dissolution.

Silica dissolution with loaded drugs could also be monitored by the release of loaded radio labeled drugs, but to discriminate between loaded and non-loaded drug a second radioisotope should be placed in the nanoparticles. For these experiments, energy discriminating SPECT would be more suitable than PET, as it allows to differentiate between two radioisotopes with

non-overlapping energy bands. Alternatively, the nanoparticles should be labeled with a PET tracer, the particle loaded with a non-labeled drug, and the biodistribution by PET compared with that of non-labeled nanoparticles loaded with the labeled drugs.

5. Conclusions and Perspectives

Understanding the phenomena ruling the degradation of MNPs in vivo is not an easy task. A lot can be learned from experiments in vitro in biological fluids that allows to rationalize the process of degradation in terms of changes in shape and size, and response to environmental conditions such as pH, ionic strength, and presence of proteins. However, conditions encountered in vivo during circulation and translocation in different organs make it difficult to predict how nanoparticles will behave in such conditions. An interesting observation from in vitro experiments confirmed in vivo is how unmodified mesoporous nanoparticles tend to degrade less than those modified with PEG or other polymers. This could be taken as a somewhat surprising result, as PEG or polymer coatings should protect the material from the medium when forming a dense and complete coating around the nanoparticles. However, in most examples of PEG functionalization, the density of PEG chains is low, which avoids protein deposition in the pores to some extent, but the pores remain exposed to water and ions from the media, eroding silica from the inside through hydrolysis. Non-coated MNPs are covered with proteins, which act as a barrier from silica hydrolysis and exchange with the medium. These phenomena seem indeed to be occurring in vivo. However, if the coating eventually degrades pores will be blocked by proteins, slowing or stopping hydrolysis. Our studies and work by other groups have provided initial insights in the degradation mechanisms of silica MNPs in vivo. Future research should tackle different variables involved in the dissolution as the diameter of the NPs, the chemistry of

oxide (including the addition of dopants), the coating nature and, most importantly, what happens when therapeutics are loaded inside the pores. For these studies PET/SPECT imaging and the development of refined radiolabelling approaches are fundamental but need to be complemented with other techniques. ICP-MS, high resolution TEM and even careful and systematic in vitro studies performed in biological fluids are further needed to gain understanding of the whole process. Mesoporous silica offer interesting possibilities for drug delivery as pores can be loaded with both hydrophobic and hydrophilic drugs as well as with biomolecules. Moreover, the silica MNPs can be easily coated with biopolymers or molecules that enhance their circulation and could provide targeting. In addition, silica will degrade and be eliminated by the organism via simple hydrolysis, i.e., only requiring an aqueous environment, contrary to enzymatic degradation needed for most degradable nanomaterials. Further understanding of the fate of mesoporous silica and of loaded drugs will be extremely beneficial for medical translation.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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- [1] J. S. Beck, J. C. Vartuli, W. J. Roth, M. E. Leonowicz, C. T. Kresge, K. D. Schmitt, C. T. W. Chu, D. H. Olson, E. W. Sheppard, S. B. McCullen, J. B. Higgins, J. L. Schlenker, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1992**, *114*, 10834.
- [2] C. T. Kresge, M. E. Leonowicz, W. J. Roth, J. C. Vartuli, J. S. Beck, *Nature* **1992**, *359*, 710.
- [3] C. J. Brinker, Y. Lu, A. Sellinger, H. Fan, *Adv. Mater.* **1999**, *11*, 579.
- [4] G. J. A. A. Soler-Illia, C. Sanchez, B. Lebeau, J. Patarin, *Chem. Rev.* **2002**, *102*, 4093.
- [5] D. Gu, F. Schuth, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2014**, *43*, 313.
- [6] P. Innocenzi, L. Malfatti, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2013**, *42*, 4198.
- [7] C. T. Kresge, W. J. Roth, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2013**, *42*, 3663.
- [8] C. Perego, R. Millini, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2013**, *42*, 3956.
- [9] M. Vallet-Regí, F. Schüth, D. Lozano, M. Colilla, M. Manzano, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2022**, *51*, 5365.
- [10] T. Wagner, S. Haffer, C. Weinberger, D. Klaus, M. Tiemann, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2013**, *42*, 4036.
- [11] A. Walcarius, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2013**, *42*, 4098.
- [12] S.-H. Wu, C.-Y. Mou, H.-P. Lin, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2013**, *42*, 3862.
- [13] G. J. A. A. Soler-Illia, P. Innocenzi, *Chem. Eur. J.* **2006**, *12*, 4478.
- [14] T. Li, S. Shi, S. Goel, X. Shen, X. Xie, Z. Chen, H. Zhang, S. Li, X. Qin, H. Yang, C. Wu, Y. Liu, *Acta Biomater.* **2019**, *89*, 1.
- [15] A. A. Ismail, D. W. Bahnemann, *J. Mater. Chem.* **2011**, *21*, 11686.
- [16] I. Sierra, D. Perez-Quintanilla, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2013**, *42*, 3792.
- [17] K. Lan, D. Zhao, *Nano Lett.* **2022**, *22*, 3177.
- [18] J. Gangadhar, B. Tirumuruhan, R. Sujith, in *Advanced Functional Porous Materials: From Macro to Nano Scale Lengths* (Eds: A. Uthaman, S. Thomas, T. Li, H. Maria), Springer International Publishing, Cham **2022**, pp. 235–258, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-85397-6_8.
- [19] P. Verma, Y. Kuwahara, K. Mori, R. Raja, H. Yamashita, *Nanoscale* **2020**, *12*, 11333.
- [20] Q. Lei, J. Guo, A. Nouredine, A. Wang, S. Wuttke, C. J. Brinker, W. Zhu, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2020**, *30*, 1909539.
- [21] T. L. Nguyen, Y. Choi, J. Kim, *Adv. Mater.* **2019**, *31*, 1803953.
- [22] B. G. Trewyn, S. Giri, I. I. Slowing, V. S. Y. Lin, *Chem. Commun.* **2007**, *2007*, 3236.
- [23] Y. Chen, J. Shi, *Adv. Mater.* **2016**, *28*, 3235.
- [24] J. Wen, K. Yang, F. Liu, H. Li, Y. Xu, S. Sun, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2017**, *46*, 6024.
- [25] Y. Wang, Q. Zhao, N. Han, L. Bai, J. Li, J. Liu, E. Che, L. Hu, Q. Zhang, T. Jiang, S. Wang, *Nanomed.: Nanotechnol. Biol. Med.* **2015**, *11*, 313.
- [26] M. Faustini, L. Nicole, E. Ruiz-Hitzky, C. Sanchez, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2018**, *28*, 1704158.
- [27] M. Vallet-Regí, F. Balas, D. Arcos, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.* **2007**, *46*, 7548.
- [28] S. Inagaki, Y. Fukushima, K. Kuroda, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.* **1993**, *1993*, 680.
- [29] A. da Cruz Schneid, L. J. C. Albuquerque, G. B. Mondo, M. Ceolin, A. S. Picco, M. B. Cardoso, *J. Sol.-Gel. Sci. Technol.* **2022**, *102*, 41.
- [30] J. G. Croissant, Y. Fatieiev, N. M. Khashab, *Adv. Mater.* **2017**, *29*, 1604634.
- [31] J. L. Paris, M. Colilla, I. Izquierdo-Barba, M. Manzano, M. Vallet-Regí, *J. Mater. Sci.* **2017**, *52*, 8761.
- [32] F. Chen, S. Goel, H. F. Valdovinos, H. Luo, R. Hernandez, T. E. Barnhart, W. Cai, *ACS Nano* **2015**, *9*, 7950.
- [33] E. Bindini, M. A. Ramirez, X. Rios, U. Cossío, C. Simó, V. Gomez-Vallejo, G. Soler-Illia, J. Llop, S. E. Moya, *Small* **2021**, *17*, 2101519.
- [34] Y. Choi, J. E. Lee, J. H. Lee, J. H. Jeong, J. Kim, *Langmuir* **2015**, *31*, 6457.
- [35] J. D. Bass, D. Grosso, C. Boissiere, E. Belamie, T. Coradin, C. Sanchez, *Chem. Mater.* **2007**, *19*, 4349.
- [36] T. Fontecave, C. Sanchez, T. Azais, C. Boissière, *Chem. Mater.* **2012**, *24*, 4326.
- [37] T. Fontecave, C. Boissiere, N. Baccile, F. J. Plou, C. Sanchez, *Chem. Mater.* **2013**, *25*, 4671.
- [38] E. Bindini, Z. Chehadi, M. Faustini, P.-A. Albouy, D. Grosso, A. Cattoni, C. Chanéac, O. Azzaroni, C. Sanchez, C. Boissière, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2020**, *12*, 13598.
- [39] S. Alberti, P. Y. Steinberg, G. Giménez, H. Amenitsch, G. Ybarra, O. Azzaroni, P. C. Angelomé, G. J. A. A. Soler-Illia, *Langmuir* **2019**, *35*, 6279.
- [40] J. Morrone, J. I. Ramallo, C. Boissière, P. C. Angelomé, M. C. Fuentes, *Chem. Mater.* **2023**, *35*, 8897.
- [41] C.-Y. Lin, C.-M. Yang, M. Lindén, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2022**, *608*, 995.
- [42] I. Izquierdo-Barba, M. Colilla, M. Manzano, M. Vallet-Regí, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* **2010**, *132*, 442.
- [43] K. Möller, T. Bein, *Chem. Mater.* **2019**, *31*, 4364.
- [44] M. A. Ramírez, E. Bindini, P. Moretti, G. J. A. A. Soler Illia, H. Amenitsch, P. Andreozzi, M. G. Ortore, S. E. Moya, *Colloids Surf., B* **2022**, *219*, 112797.

- [45] A. Di, J. Schmitt, N. Elstone, T. Arnold, K. J. Edler, *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* **2022**, *341*, 112018.
- [46] R. Rampado, S. Crotti, P. Caliceti, S. Pucciarelli, M. Agostini, *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* **2020**, *8*, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fbioe.2020.00166>.
- [47] G. Bashiri, M. S. Padilla, K. L. Swingle, S. J. Shepherd, M. J. Mitchell, K. Wang, *Lab Chip* **2023**, *23*, 1432.
- [48] J. Ren, N. Andrikopoulos, K. Velonia, H. Tang, R. Cai, F. Ding, P. C. Ke, C. Chen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2022**, *144*, 9184.
- [49] I. Kuschnerus, K. Giri, J. Ruan, Y. Huang, N. Bedford, A. Garcia-Bennett, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* **2022**, *612*, 467.
- [50] R. Madathiparambil Visalakshan, L. E. González García, M. R. Benzigar, A. Ghazaryan, J. Simon, A. Mierczynska-Vasilev, T. D. Michl, A. Vinu, V. Mailänder, S. Morsbach, K. Landfester, K. Vasilev, *Small* **2020**, *16*, 2000285.
- [51] C. Vidaurre-Agut, E. Rivero-Buceta, E. Romaní-Cubells, A. M. Clemments, C. D. Vera-Donoso, C. C. Landry, P. Botella, *ACS Omega* **2019**, *4*, 8852.
- [52] A. M. Clemments, P. Botella, C. C. Landry, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2015**, *7*, 21682.
- [53] J. Llop, T. Lammers, *ACS Nano* **2021**, *15*, 16974.
- [54] Q. Zhang, X. Wang, P.-Z. Li, K. T. Nguyen, X.-J. Wang, Z. Luo, H. Zhang, N. S. Tan, Y. Zhao, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2014**, *24*, 2450.
- [55] P. Dogra, N. L. Adolphi, Z. Wang, Y.-S. Lin, K. S. Butler, P. N. Durfee, J. G. Croissant, A. Nouredine, E. N. Coker, E. L. Bearer, V. Cristini, C. J. Brinker, *Nat. Commun.* **2018**, *9*, 4551.
- [56] F. Chen, H. Hong, Y. Zhang, H. F. Valdovinos, S. Shi, G. S. Kwon, C. P. Theuer, T. E. Barnhart, W. Cai, *ACS Nano* **2013**, *7*, 9027.
- [57] M. A. Ramírez, ÁM Martínez-Villacorta, V. Gómez-Vallejo, P. Andreozzi, G. Soler-Illia, J. Llop, S. E. Moya, *Nanoscale Adv.* **2022**, *4*, 2098.
- [58] H. L. Kim, S. B. Lee, H. J. Jeong, D. W. Kim, *RSC Adv.* **2014**, *4*, 31318.
- [59] Q. He, Z. Zhang, F. Gao, Y. Li, J. Shi, *Small* **2011**, *7*, 271.
- [60] Y.-S. Lin, N. Abadeer, K. R. Hurley, C. L. Haynes, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2011**, *133*, 20444.

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